

Spectroscopic Studies and Some Physical Properties of Some Metal Biphthalocyanine Compounds

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Manuscript received 19 October 1981, revised 16 November 1982, accepted 19 March 1983

The magnetic susceptibility of some metal biphthalocyanines is studied within the temperature range of 300-400 K. The values of the effective magnetic moment, μ_{eff} , Curie constant C and Curie-Weiss constant θ are determined. The data of the dielectric constant are collected for Fe-biphthalocyanine. The infrared spectra of the solid chelates are also studied. The results are discussed in the light of the molecular structure of the compounds.

MACROCYCLIC compounds containing four pyrrole units are of commercial importance in the manufacture of coloured pigments. Naturally occurring haemoglobin, chlorophyll and the phthalocyanines belong to this class of compounds¹.

Metal phthalocyanine (I) was prepared as early as 1907 in which the metal could be one of a variety of transition or main group metallic ions². The structural properties of phthalocyanine have been discussed in detail over the last 20 years.

Metal biphthalocyanines (II) have been prepared³ by the partial replacement of the bifunctional phthalic anhydride by pyromellitic dianhydride in such a manner as to prevent the formation of polymeric structure and to minimize the alkali sensitivity.

The aim of the present work is to study the physical properties of the biphthalocyanine compounds and to give an outline about the ir analysis of these compounds with respect to those of phthalocyanine compounds.

The magnetic properties of both phthalocyanine and biphthalocyanine compounds refer to the bonding of the central metal atom with the four surrounding isoindole nitrogen atoms which form the corners of a square around the central metal atom. The advantage of magnetic measurements, when used for the study of chemical bonding, relates to the information on one atom and its immediate surroundings with no additional information from the rest of the molecule. The magnetic properties of phthalocyanines are of further interest, because of the similarity of the central portion of phthalocyanine, chlorophyll and haemoglobin molecules.

The diamagnetic anisotropy⁴ of aromatic hydrocarbons has been the subject of extensive study, both experimental and theoretical, since the time their highly anisotropic character was discovered. Pauling⁵ assumed that the diamagnetic anisotropy of the benzene ring was due to the mobile ($2\rho\pi$) electrons of the carbon atoms. It has also become apparent that the σ electrons may contribute appreciably to the diamagnetic anisotropy⁶⁻⁸.

The first measurements of magnetic properties of phthalocyanines were taken by Klemm and Klemm⁹. The effective magnetic moments of nickel and copper phthalocyanines as calculated by them are -0.30 and 1.73 B.M. Ray and Sen¹⁰ investigated the magnetic properties of more than thirty copper complexes including copper phthalocyanine, using the Gouy method.

The susceptibility of Ni(II) phthalocyanine¹¹ indicated that the complex is diamagnetic, having eight d electrons in the four lower orbitals.

The results obtained by Orgel¹² on Fe(II) phthalocyanine showed that the complex obeys the Curie-Weiss law. The Curie Weiss temperature was found to be 9 K indicating that the compound is weak ferromagnetic.

Lever¹³ found that the derived value of the Bohr magneton number for the Fe(II) complex is intermediate between the spin values for two unpaired electrons and four unpaired electrons, respectively.

Experimental

Metal phthalocyanines (I) were prepared by the urea fusion technique¹⁴ as described in Paint Technology Manual. A mixture of phthalic anhydride (4 mole), metal chloride (1 mole) and urea (excess) in presence of ammonium molybdate as a

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catalyst was fused together and the fusion continued until a highly coloured mass developed. The reaction mass was then allowed to cool, pulverised and washed several times with dil. HCl, distilled water, ethanol and ether and dried at 105° for 3 hr. This was subjected to further purification by sublimation.

(I) Metal phthalocyanine.

Metal biphthalocyanines⁸ were prepared also by the urea fusion technique. A mixture of phthalic anhydride (6 mole), pyromellitic dianhydride (1 mole), metal chloride (2 mole) and urea (excess) was fused together in presence of ammonium molybdate as catalyst. The method used to obtain the metal phthalocyanines was used to get the product.

The magnetic susceptibility of some metal biphthalocyanines (Cu, Fe, Ni and Sn) was measured by the Gouy method. The samples in the form of fine powder were packed uniformly in glass tube \approx

15 cm long and 0.4 cm i.d. The data were collected in a magnetic field of 3000 Oe. A non-inductive furnace was used to heat up the sample. The temperature was measured by using copper constant thermocouple with reference junction at 0.0°.

The dielectric constant was measured by using RFT bridge type 1007, ranging from 1 to 10⁴ P. F. The electrical conductivity of Ni-biphthalocyanine was also measured in the same temperature range.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic susceptibility of copper-biphthalocyanine is measured at room temperature. The effective magnetic moment is found to be 1.71 B.M. which lies in the range of Cu²⁺ in its complexes¹⁵.

Fig. 1a shows the corrected (for diamagnetism) molar magnetic susceptibility for Fe-biphthalocyanine from room temperature to 400 K. It is obvious that there is a shoulder around 340 K, indicating some sort of structural phase transition. Fig. 1b correlate the reciprocal molar magnetic susceptibility with temperature when two straight lines are obtained, line I with magnetic constant, C (Curie constant) = 5.3, Curie-Weiss constant (θ) = 0 K and effective magnetic moment $\mu_{eff} = 6.52$ B.M. ; line II with

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of susceptibility of Fe-biphthalocyanine.

(II) Metal biphthalocyanine.

$C=6.0$, $\theta=-120$ K and $\mu_{eff}=6.75$ B.M. The negative θ values indicate that the interaction is antiferromagnetic which agrees with the values obtained for Fe-complexes¹⁰ such as $(RNH_2)_2-FeCl_4$ where $(R=CH_3, C_2H_5, \dots)$.

Fig. 2a shows the temperature dependence of susceptibility for Ni-bipthalocyanine compound. The data are collected within 300-400 K and in a magnetic field of 300 Oe. The magnetic constants of this compound, as calculated from Fig. 2b are $C=0.21$, $\theta = +290$ K and $\mu_{eff}=1.29$ B.M. The positive θ value indicates the existence of ferromagnetic interaction.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of susceptibility of Ni-bipthalocyanine.

The magnetic susceptibility measurement for Sn-bipthalocyanine shows that the compound is diamagnetic and nearly temperature independent in the range of 300-400 K. The values of the molar magnetic susceptibility at room temperature and the effective magnetic moments are -395.636×10^{-6} and -0.31 B.M., respectively.

Owing to the expected structural transition in the magnetic susceptibility measurements for Fe-bipthalocyanine, the dielectric constant measurements were carried out in the temperature range of 300-420 K (Fig 3). It is obvious from the figure

Fig. 3. Temperature dependence of dielectric constant (ϵ) of Fe-bipthalocyanine.

that there is a broad hump around 340 K which is the same temperature at which the anomaly in the susceptibility curve occurs. Table I shows the values of the magnetic moments for the phthalocyanine and bipthalocyanine compounds.

TABLE I—THE VALUES OF THE MAGNETIC MOMENTS IN B.M.

Metal ion	Effective magnetic moment in B.M.	
	(I) metal phthalo.	(II) metal bipthalo.
Cu	1.73 ⁶	1.71
Fe	3.96	6.52
Ni	0.0 ¹⁷	1.29
Sn	—	-0.31

The electrical conductivity measurements shown in Fig. 4 indicate that the behaviour obeys the well known Arrhenious relation $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp. (-E/KT)$, where E is the activation energy, K the Boltzman constant, T the absolute temperature and σ_0 is a constant. The value of E is calculated from the figure and is found to be 0.36 eV, which indicates the semiconducting properties of the compound.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of conductivity of Ni-bipthalocyanine.

Infrared spectra of the metal phthalocyanines were studied in detail by Ebert and Gottlieb¹⁰.

An analysis of the infrared spectra of the metal bipthalocyanines gives a good information about the structure of the compounds. The ir spectra

(Fig. 5) of the compounds show a broad band at 3230, 3225, 3450 and 3225 cm^{-1} for Sn, Fe, Cu and Ni, respectively. The bands in this region¹⁰ are usually due to various NH stretching vibration. The $-C=C-H$ group has a C-H stretching vibra-

Fig. 5. The ir spectra of some metal biphthalocyanine compounds.

tion which absorbs near 3300 cm^{-1} . This band is not as broad as the alcoholic bonded C-H bands found in this region. The C-H stretching vibration of olefins, aromatic rings and three membered rings absorb mainly in the region above 3000 cm^{-1} . Compounds containing C=C group absorb at $1660\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Compounds containing C=N group absorb usually at 1690 cm^{-1} . This region is of interest, since bands due to N=N and C=C may be in the region of $1600\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The fundamental studies on the benzene vibrations have shown that the unsaturated carbon-carbon stretching vibration of the three double bonds around the ring result in a resonance splitting effect on the absorption bands.

Little is known about the characteristics of the infrared absorption bands arising from the N=N-linkage. By analogy with the C=N and C=C groups, such bands might be expected to appear in the 1600 cm^{-1} but it would likely be weak unless conjugated, and might be absent in highly symmetrical structures. The medium to weak bands found in the $1600\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region can be due to the

skeletal vibration. Bands due to stretching vibration of C-N may occur within $1400\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Other bands in this region are C-H in-plane deformation assignments for C-N band. The assignments of metal biphthalocyanine complexes are shown in Table 2.

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TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENT OF METAL BIPHthalOCYANINE COMPLEXES.

So-Biph.	Fe-Biph.	Cu-Biph.	Ni-Biph.	Vibration assignment
3230 b	3225 b	3450 b	3220 b	C—C—H
1340 b	1330	1330	1325	C—N
1125 m	1125	1120	1130 m	C—C—N
725 s	725 s	720 s	730 s	CH of 4 adjacent H ring atoms

b = broad, m = medium s = strong. Absorption frequencies are in cm^{-1} .